

Make in India - An Analysis of IT Sector

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ABSTRACT

IT-BPM sector in India which has 56% of the global outsourcing market size is a rapidly growing urban infrastructure sector. This sector contributes a largest share in Total Indian Service exports which is 45%. IT-BPM sector is the largest private sector employer which provides 3.7 million jobs across the globe and contributes 9.3% of India's GDP. Govt. of India is working towards the improvement of the infrastructure, which shows that it might be a reason of obstacle in the path of Make-In-India. Adequate attention was not given to the Indian IT industry with respect to Global IT industry, for which it is observed that the study and research regarding Indian IT-BPM sector is still relatively inexperienced. However to overcome this and to make successful IT-BPM sector in India, we need to understand the importance and build the development of IT in India as IT sector in developing countries. The objective of this study is to emphasize on the game plan of India IT-BPM sector to stay on top of the growth curve through its earnings, innovative service providing, job creation and skill development to manage the updated technology. The study also suggests certain measures to be taken to make the initiative encouraging for the industry as well as for the investors. It includes Improvement of the Infrastructure, employment reforms, Strive towards skill building and efficient workforce, Investment in Research and Development, Adding value to the innovations continuously to fulfil the changing expectations of customers. The country today is turning towards digital India with consistent innovation in products, process and business models that can deliver enhanced value to the clients to remain as an excellent business centre for IT-BPM industry. If it improves with the help of Make-In-India initiative India can remain in the leadership position in the global market and can provide highest volume of employment and career growth opportunities in India.

Keywords: IT-BPM Sector, Information Technology & Business Process Management Sector, Growth Curve, Employment Reforms, Innovations.

INTRODUCTION

The honourable Prime Minister of India Mr. Narendra Modi has initiated a concept of "Make in India" in the year 2014 which aims to boost up manufacturing by easing the business process. This may also attract the foreign companies to set up their industries in India as well as to investment more in the growth and development of the infrastructure of the nation. The ultimate vision of Make in India is to create employment opportunities for the innumerable unemployed of India.

The success of every business organisation depends on certain factors such as accurate analysis, choosing the right technology and the future vision. It has been observed since last two decade that the organisations, who have invested more in technology, have chosen the path of innovation, increase in market share, financial figures and overall competitiveness. Information Technology is the only technology which provides the opportunities to analyse specific data and planning of business journey accordingly. Everybody is aware of the growth that the IT sector now a days is performing. The single sector in India, which is developing in a rapid speed, is IT sector. India proudly holds the third position in the list of start up hubs, which has already encouraged 4200 start ups in the country. The total revenue generated by this sector is USD 130 million. With the help of Make in India this sector has witnessed the highest growth since last 5 year in 2015, which has registered an approximate growth of 13.5%. The aim of the government for investing in this sector is to make India, a technology driven country. The digital India campaign of govt. Focuses on providing mobile connectivity throughout and e-delivery citizen services.

Information Technology and Business Process Management sector in India consists of 56% of the global outsourcing market size. It is a rapidly growing urban infrastructure which has fostered several IT centres in the country. This sector contributes a largest share in Total Indian Service exports which is 45%. IT-BPM sector is the largest private sector employer which provides 3.7 million jobs across the globe and contributes 9.3% of India's GDP. With the development of IT-BPM sector employment opportunities will raise and the people will become more knowledgeable in the technology.

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RATIONALE

Different phases of journey of IT-BPM sector in India.

Pre 1995 - During early 90's US based IT companies started outsourcing the work due to low cost and skilled talent pool in India.

1995-2005 - During this period huge investments were made in the IT industry in its R & D and infrastructure. Number of firms started growing in size in India and also started offering various services to management and help them in formulation market strategies. Even the Western firms set up a number of captives in India.

2005-2016 - During this period Indian IT industries became multinational companies which has a number of delivery centres across the globe. Nearly 670 off share development centres are providing their services in more than 80 countries in the world. The revenue in IT-BPM sector in India was expected to reach USD 160 billion in year 2016. Also there was an expectation of increase in employment which is up to 3.7 million people directly and 10 million indirectly as of FY 2016. This industry is considered as the 3rd largest start up base in India with nearly 4200 start ups in the FY 2016.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study are:

1. To evaluate the status of IT sector across the globe with special reference to India.
2. To determine the impact of Make in India on IT sector.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sources of Data: Basically the secondary sources have been used for data collection for the study. Variables such as global economy, Currency, Inflation, Political, Market environment, Technology up gradation, Innovations, Diversification, Modernisation, Mobility of Skilled Professionals etc are taken into consideration for such analysis.

Sample Design: The study has been done taking Tata Consultancy Services as a sample. As it is the oldest and largest IT industry in India, the impact of Make in India on this industry can be better judged than any other company. The profitability of the TCS company is nearly 40% of the total profit generated by top five IT companies in India. Even keeping in mind the market size of this industry, sales, total assets, Enterprise value this company has been selected as a sample for analysis of data.

Period of the Study: As the study is done for performance, growth, employment, new start ups in India during Pre and post make in India stage the time period has been considered from the FY 2010 to 2016. The study has been analysed between Pre make in India period which is from 2010 - 2013 and post make in India period which is from 2014 - 2016.

Statistical Tools: The statistical tools used for the analysis of data are Percentage, Ratio, Graphs etc.

ANALYSIS

There are huge numbers of IT companies across the globe. In comparison to that India's IT business constitutes 7% of the global IT business. The number of IT industries established in India as of now is 70. Out of these top 5 IT Companies have their branches located most of major cities in of the different states. In Odisha there are 6 IT companies running their IT business, which is developing the technological skill and requirements for the people of Odisha.

Table -1: Employment & Growth

Year	Indian Talent Pool (in millions)	Employment in IT Industry (in millions)	Growth of GIC (in numbers)
2010	3.7	2.3	710
2011	4.0	2.5	730
2012	4.4	2.8	760
2013	4.7	3.0	790
2014	5.3	3.3	825
2015	5.8	3.5	1025
2016	6.0	3.7	1050

Source: Self Compiled

Indian Talent Pool

Due to the implementation of Make-In-India, a huge expectation was created for the young mass; the chance of getting quality and large employment becoming easy. So the large number of young talents entered into the field of IT academics, which forced them to learn more and more as well as developing their skills in the field of IT. Here from the above table it can be observed that the total number of 16.8 million young talents entered into IT field during last four years (i.e. from 2010 to 2013) just before the Make-In-India programme. After this programme this number has gone up to 17.1 million in three consecutive years i.e. from 2014 to 2016, which is more than the total of previous 4 years. So there is a huge demand for IT sectors among the young talents of India.

Employment

Growth is also found in case of employment in IT industry due to the impact of Make-In-India. Irrespective of recession in the market and even though there was huge retrenchment in different industries demand for employment in IT sector is found more and more in different years. It was observed that for the years 2010, 2011, 2012 & 2013 the total employment is 1043 million whereas after Make-In-India programme the employment reached up to 10.5 million for the year 2014, 2015 & 2016. The employment growth is found in post Make-In-India period, which was considered for only three years. And this is even more than the employment generated in last four years during pre Make-In-India stage. So we can infer that the impact of Make-In-India on IT sector for generating employment is a responsible variable.

Growth of Global In House Centres (GIC)

GIC also known as captive centres, contributing almost 20% in exports. The total GIC in India generating a revenue of USD 22 billion and created an employment opportunity of 0.79 million manpower. The impact of Make-In-India programme is also clearly imagined from the growth of number of GIC in India, which is increasing in a huge gap of growth rate in 2014 and 2015. North American companies as well as European companies are the major investors in the captive segment in India and they constitute nearly 90% of the total captive in India.

CASE STUDY OF TCS

TCS is the first software service company in India, established in the year 1968 as an IT services providing organisation. It deals with IT services, consulting business Solution Company. It represents a major share of Indian IT industry's combined market capitalisation. It is one of the largest MNC in India which spreads its business across America, Europe, Asia-Pacific, Middle East & Africa. It has achieved several achievements like in 2016 it has won three Silver Stevie's at 14th Annual American Business Awards, in 2015 - Won Gold, Silver & Bronze Stevie's at American Business Awards, in 2013 - Best Performing Consultancy brand award in Europe and Red Hat North America Awards for system integrator partner of the year.

Table - 2: Revenue of Leading IT Players in India in the FY 2016

Company	Revenue (USD Billion)
TCS	16.6
Infosys	9.5
Wipro	7.8
HCL Tech	4.7
Tech Mahindra	4.04

Source: Self Compiled

TCS's financial performance on 2011-12 was USD 10 billion which on today's date the companies like Infosys, Wipro, HCL Tech, Tech Mahindra are not able to reach at this figure individually. The financial performances for the financial year 2013, 2014, 2015 & 2016 are USD 12, 13.5, 15.7 & 16.6 billion respectively.

Table - 3: Market size of IT Industries in India (USD Billion)

Year	Domestic	Export	Total
2010	24	50	74
2011	29	59	88
2012	32	69	101
2013	32	76	108
2014	32	86	118
2015	48	98.5	146.6
2016	52	108	160

Source: Self Compiled

The market size of TCS company is 10.4% of the total Indian IT & ITeS sector. Top 5 IT companies such as TCS, Infosys, Wipro, HCL Tech and Tech Mahindra contribute 25% to the total IT industry revenue in which TCS plays a major role. Better analysis can be made from different other variables of TCS company, which is as follows:

Table- 4: Growth Prospects of IT

Year	Sales (Rs. In Crore)	Total Asset (Rs. In Crore)	Enterprise Value (Rs. In Crore)
2010	30029	27394	148664
2011	37325	32681	227365
2012	48894	41394	223533
2013	62990	52267	301869
2014	81812	67138	403380
2015	94652	73661	481762
2016	108647	89384	489675

Source: Self Compiled

Sales

So far as sales are concerned it has drastically increased after Make-In-India programme. The total sales of post Make-In-India stage for three years are 60% more than the total sales of last four years during pre Make-In-India period. It is even observed in the year 2014 the sale volume has increased by 30% over 2013, which is considered as the highest growth rate immediately after Make-In-India programme. So the impact is clearly visible in the year 2014, 2015 & 2016.

Total Assets

The impact of Make-In-India programme can be better analysed from the total asset employed in the company.

The total asset of the organisation refers to the financial soundness and efficiency of the organisation which is even better than the previous years. It is observed that the total asset employed during post Make-In-India programme is 50% more than the total assets of last four years during pre Make-In-India programme. Even the growth rate observed in the year 2014 just after implementation of Make-In-India is 28.5%, which is again highest among all years.

Enterprise Value

The value of enterprise is also increasing year after year. The total value of enterprise from 2010 to 2013 is Rs. 9, 01,431 crore where as the value from 2014 to 2016 amounted to Rs. 13, 74,817 crore, which is 52.5% more than the earlier value. During the year 2014 the growth is found 34% over 2013 which is considered as the highest growth as of now.

FINDINGS

Though the employment has reached up to 3.7 million, still the growth in this sector was not up to expectation after Make in India programme. It is a usual growth rate over number of years, which is not a clear cut result of Make-In-India programme. There is no significant increase of employment growth rate, which can be summarised as an effect of make-In-India. So the purpose of creating huge employment through Make-In-India did not prove good here. Similarly the young talents of India entering into IT sector are not showing a significant growth rate after Make-In-India programme. Though the number of Indian talent pool is increasing in each year, yet it can't be clearly identified how much percentage growth has taken place due to make-In-India process. Though India has excellence in business delivery with diversified talent and strong network, lack of infrastructure, effective collaboration and partnership restricting this sector to succeed.

SUGGESTIONS

As Indian IT industry is able to provide better services at a relatively less cost as compared to US market, but it is behind in the domestic market. Though there are many good reasons to boost up this sector in India, it depends on the states, which we are looking at. Infrastructures in certain states are growing up and they are forcing the IT centres being set up in such states. So this has to be considered because Make-In-India is a central government initiative. As India is a hub for digital skills, which requires skill set development and focused training on digital solutions. This sector can provide better services related to customer, product development, sales and marketing areas where India has the capability and skills to grow in the sector and add further value to the economy. Employment reforms as well as large investments are also required in Research & Development area of this sector.

CONCLUSION

Government has recognised the need of the improvement of IT services domestically and included IT among the sectors in Make-In-India, which not only helps the urban to develop but makes the rural areas to get penetrated related to employment and other related services. IT services and software products are the next fast growing segments after e-commerce segment, so that there is a large scope for growth, which requires a push in the direction from the government to compete effectively in the globalised world.

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